

Urinary schistosomiasis among residents of Kiri in Shelleng Local Government Area of Adamawa State, Nigeria

Stephen K. Tidi *

Department of Biological Sciences, Federal University Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The study determined the prevalence of urinary schistosomiasis among Kiri community in Shelleng Local Government area of Adamawa State. Two hundred and sixty four samples were collected from the residents. Macroscopic examination for haematuria and concentration technique for the detection of *S. haematobium* was employed. Result showed the prevalence of (76.1%). Males had higher (78.1%) infection than females (70.8%). The age bracket of 21-25 years (84.6%) were more infected than other age groups, and least infected were 0-5 years (69.2%). However, there was no significant difference with respect to age and sex ($p>0.05$). Participants who had contact with water greater than four times in a day (100.0%) were more infected, whereas those who had contact twice in a day (67.5%) were least ($p>0.05$). Macroscopic examination of urine samples were bloody (81.8%) with females (91.6%) higher than males (78.1%) ($p>0.05$). Prevalence of haematuria was more in the age bracket 11-15 years (100.0%) and least among 5-10 years (75.0%). These differences in the prevalence rate was not significant ($p>0.05$). Haematuria in urine compared to parasitological detection of *S. haematobium* indicated sensitivity of 83.3%, specificity 42.8%, positive predictive value 83.3%, negative predictive value 56.2% and percentage accuracy of 78.4%. The presence of macroscopic blood in urine was a reliable diagnostic tool for *S. haematobium* infection, because the difference was insignificant with parasitological method. The sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value and percentage accuracy are reliable in places where resources for diagnosis of *S. haematobium* is insufficient. This study revealed that Kiri community in Shelleng Local Government Area of Adamawa State was highly endemic with urinary schistosomiasis posing danger to health of the people. There is the need for immediate intervention by all stake holders in health in various arms of government. This include mass distribution of praziquantel to infected persons and health education.

Citation: Tidi SK (2015). Urinary schistosomiasis among residents of Kiri in Shelleng Local Government Area of Adamawa State, Nigeria. *Journal of Environmental Toxicology and Public Health* 1: 18-24.

Received October 17, 2015; **Accepted** October 26, 2015; **Published** November 4, 2015.

Copyright: © 2015 Tidi SK. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited. JETPH is a journal publication of BRSF.

Competing Interests: The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

* **E-mail:** stephentiddi@yahoo.com

Keywords: *Schistosoma haematobium*, urinary schistosomiasis, water contacts, Kiri, Nigeria

1. INTRODUCTION

Schistosomiasis, also known as bilharziasis or "snail fever," is a waterborne parasitic infection that damages internal organs such as urinary bladder and liver [1]. Schistosomiasis is a parasitic disease caused by blood flukes (trematodes) of the genus *Schistosoma*, sometimes referred to as bilharziasis, or snail fever [2]. After malaria and intestinal helminthiasis, schistosomiasis happened to be the third most devastating tropical disease in the world, being a major source of morbidity and mortality for developing countries in Africa, South America, the Caribbean, the Middle East, and Asia [3]. Infection is acquired when people

come into contact with fresh water infested with the larval forms (cercariae) of parasitic blood flukes, known as schistosomes, often through daily activities such as bathing, washing, laundry, and fetching. Children become vulnerable to infection while playing in mud and water that harbours the snail host of schistosomiasis.

Schistosomiasis is classified as a neglected tropical disease. It is a disease of poverty that leads to chronic ill-health. The infection is prevalent in tropical and sub-tropical areas, in poor communities without potable water and adequate sanitation. More than 207 million people, 85% of who live in Africa, are infected

with the disease, and an estimated 700 million people are at risk of infection in 76 countries where the disease is considered endemic, as their agricultural work, domestic chores, and recreational activities expose them to infested water. Globally, 200,000 deaths are attributed to schistosomiasis annually [4,5]. The infectious agent is responsible for urogenital schistosomiasis, it infects over 112 million people annually in Sub-Saharan Africa alone. It is also responsible for 32 million cases of dysuria, 10 million cases of hydronephrosis, and 150,000 deaths from renal failure annually, making *S. haematobium* the world's deadliest schistosome [6].

In Brazil and Africa especially in Nigeria refugee movements due to insecurity and migration to urban areas are introducing the disease to new locations where it has not existed. Increasing population size and corresponding needs for irrigation farming, hydroelectric power and water supply have led to increased transmission. Infections are not uniformly distributed within communities because of differences in knowledge, attitudes and practices on hygiene. It has been estimated that 5-10% of an endemic community may be heavily infected, and the remainder has mild to moderate infections. The risk of infection is highest amongst those who lived near lakes, rivers or dams where water activities are daily carried out [7]. In Nigeria, wide distribution of urinary schistosomiasis has been reported. Bala *et. al.* [8] reported 74.0% from Gusau Zamfara State, 83.3% From Niger [9], 15.0% from Bali Taraba State, Monday *et. al.* [10], 61.7% from Ogun State [11].

The World Health Organization has developed guidelines for community treatment based on the impact of the disease in villages in which it is common: When a village reports more than 50 percent of children have blood in their urine, everyone in the village receives treatment. When 20 to 50 percent of children have bloody urine, only school-age children are treated. When fewer than 20 percent of children have symptoms, mass treatment is not implemented [12].

In Nigeria, the National Control Programme on schistosomiasis has planned to reduce the burden of the disease by 50% through the use of mass distribution of praziquantel in endemic areas. However, little success has been achieved due to lack of baseline data in the distribution of the disease. To succeed in this control, it is important to provide adequate information on the epidemiological data among the endemic communities. Previous studies in Adamawa State for urinary schistosomiasis indicated high prevalence of the disease in some areas [13,14,15], but lack of baseline data on the distribution of the disease in a wide scale has hampered its control, as such data from different communities will help to identify high-risk areas for treatment and health education. This study is aimed to determine urinary

schistosomiasis in Kiri community of Adamawa State using parasitological and questionnaire methods.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Study area

The study area was Kiri community located in Shelleng Local Government Area of Adamawa State. Shelleng is situated along latitude 9° 53'51N and longitude 12° 0'32E greenwich meridian with population of 148, 490 [16]. It shares borders with Borno State to the north, Song L.G.A to the East, Demsa L.G.A to the south and Guyuk L.G.A to the West. Kiri dam is situated in Shelleng L.G.A. The dam was constructed in 1982 for the purpose of irrigation, hydroelectric power generation and water supply to Savannah Sugar company Numan. The major water supply to the dam is from Dadin Kowa dam in Gombe State, and it is a tributary to river Benue via River Gongola. The population around the Kiri dam consists of cluster of compounds each surrounded by local made mats and mud wall. The compounds are situated 50-100 metres away from the Dam. The main occupation is mainly fishing with a small number of the population engaged in petty trading and cattle rearing. Crop production is difficult in the area because of crashes of hippopotamus from the dam that usually engage in the destruction of crops. The fishermen are mainly Kanakuru. There are also other tribes, like the lunguda, Bachama, Hausa, Bura, Jukun and Jenjo. The inhabitants come in contact with the dam on daily basis for different purposes including fishing, bathing, washing and collecting water for domestic use. There is no health clinic and sanitary infrastructure such as clean drinking water and latrine, if present they are poorly constructed. The only borehole available is competitive and is controlled. In preference the dam is used by residents for different purposes. As a result of poor sanitary infrastructure most people defaecate and urinate indiscriminately thereby contaminating the environment near the dam. With an open vegetation of shrubs and herbaceous plants much favoured by animals, the closeness of Savannah Sugar Company that provides foliage for animal use; the dam is conducive for the nomadic Fulani in dry season and serves as a major campsite and stop post in the nomadic North-South migration.

2.2 Data and Sample Collection

2.2.1 Data Collection

The data collection was by questionnaire administration. Two hundred and sixty four (264) Individuals was randomly selected for the questionnaire administration. The body of the questionnaire included the biodata followed by respondents number of water contacts each day. Under-five children were interviewed through their parents/guardians.

2.2.2 Sample Collection

Two hundred and sixty four urine samples were collected from the volunteers in a 30ml universal containers between 10 am-2pm each day with instruction that they were to include last few drops of urine. Each bottle was labeled to correspond to the person's biodata form. The sample were preserved by adding sodium hypochlorite [17]. The sample were transported to Federal Medical Centre Yola for examination.

2.3 Sample Analysis

Macroscopic examination of the samples were done to detect the presence of blood and clarity of urine eexample clear or amber. The samples were analysed as reported by Cheesbrough [17]. 2 drops of saponin solution was added to samples that contain visible blood to lyze the red cells. The method involved the use of polycarbonate filter. The filter holder was assambled and attached to the end of a 10ml syringe. The plunger was removed and the syringe filled with urine to 10ml mark. The plunger was replaced back. Holding the syringe over a container, urine was gently pass through the filter. The filter holder was removed and unscrewed. Using blunt-ended forceps, the filter was transfered face upward to a slide. A drop of physiological saline was added and covered with a cover slip. The entire filter was examined under x10 objective lens. The number of eggs were counted and reported as number of eggs per 10ml of urine.

2.4 Ethical Consideration

Permission was obtained from Ministry of Environment and Rural Development, and Shelleng Local governemnt primary health care. Consent was obtained from each volunteer before the commencement of data and sample collection.

2.5 Data Analysis

Data were entered into a database created in Epidata version 3.1. Data was then transfered to statistical analysis system (SAS) version 8.0 and were analysed. Statistical significant difference were indicated by $p < 0.05$ and no statistical difference by $p > 0.05$.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Urinary schistosomiasis

Out of 264 urine samples examined for infection 201(76.1%) were infected with *Schistosoma haematobium* with males having higher infection 150(78.1%) and females 51(70.8%). However, there was no significant association in infection and sex ($p > 0.05$). Individuals in the age bracket of 21-25 years were the most infected 33(84.6%) followed by those between the age group of 26-30 years 12(80.0%). Participants between the age groups of 0-5 years 27(69.2%) and 11-15 years 24(72.7%) were the least

infected. However, there was no significant difference in infection by age ($p > 0.05$) (Table 1).

3.2 Sex related urinary schistosomiasis and Water contacts each day.

The result in table 2 shows infection of *S. haematobium* with daily number of water contacts and sex. Participants who had contacts with contaminated water greater than four times 6 (100.0%) in a day were more infected. This is followed by those who had contacts with water four times every day 27(81.8%), whereas those who had contacts with contaminated water twice 75(67.5%) in a day were the least infected. Chi-square analysis indicated that there was no significant difference in infection and number of water contacts in a day ($p > 0.05$).

3.3 Age related urinary schistosomiasis and Water contacts each day.

The result in Table 3 shows infection of *S. haematobium* with daily number of water contacts and age. Out of 201 urine samples that were infected with *S. haematobium*, 75(37.3%) of them were from those who had contacts with contaminated water twice in a day, followed by those who had contacts thrice on each day 57(28.3%). The least percentage of infection out of 201 infected persons were from those who had more than four contacts with water 6(2.9%). Infection was higher among the age brackets of >30 years and 16-20 years 36(17.9% each) respectively, whereas the least infection was between the age group of 26-30 years 12(5.9%). Chi-aquare analysis confirms that there was significant difference between infection and daily contacts with contaminated water ($p < 0.05$).

3.4 Haematuria in urinary schistosomiasis

Result in Table 4 shows that out of the 264 samples examined for haematuria 216 (81.8%) contain blood; 150 (78.1%) males and 66 (91.6%) females. There was however no significance difference in the prevalence of haematuria in relation to sex ($p > 0.05$). The prevalence of haematuria was observed to be highest in the age brackets of 11-15 years 33 (100.0%) followed by age group of 26-30 years 12 (80.0%). The least age group with reported haematuria were 5-10 years and > 30 years 36(75.0% each) respectively. These differences in the prevalence rate of haematuria was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

3.5 Haematuria compared to parastological

Result in Table 5 shows the comparison between parasitological detection of *S. haematobium* and haematuria. It was observed that of the 264 urine samples examined, 180 were infected with *S. haematobium* in the presence of haematuria. Twenty one (21) of the urine samples were positive for *S. haematobium* without any visible traces of blood. There were 36 bloody samples without detectable *S.*

haematobium. Twenty seven (27) of the samples contained neither blood nor *S. haematobium*. Analysis of the result showed that the presence of blood in urine compared to parasitological detection of *S. haematobium* was

not significant ($p > 0.05$), and indicated sensitivity of 83.3%, specificity 42.8%, positive predictive value 83.3%, negative predictive value 56.2% and percentage accuracy of 78.4%.

Table 1. Urinary schistosomiasis by age and sex

Age groups in years	Number examined			M	F	Total
	M	F	Total	No.(%) infected	No.(%) infected	No.(%) infected
0-5	27	12	39	18(66.6)	9(75.0)	27(69.2)
6-10	21	21	42	18(85.7)	15(71.4)	33(78.6)
11-15	18	15	33	15(83.3)	9(60.0)	24(72.7)
16-20	45	3	48	33(73.3)	3(100.0)	36(75.0)
21-25	36	3	39	30(83.3)	3(100.0)	33(84.6)
26-30	12	3	15	9(75.0)	3(100.0)	12(80.0)
>30	33	15	48	27(81.8)	9(60.0)	36(75.0)
Total	192	72	264	150(78.1)	51(70.8)	201(76.1)

Table 2. Urinary schistosomiasis by daily water contacts and sex

Water contacts in a day	Number examined			M	F	Total
	M	F	Total	No.(%) infected	No.(%)infected	No.(%)infected
1	21	24	45	21(100.0)	15(62.5)	36(80.0)
2	93	18	111	63(67.7)	12(66.6)	75(67.5)
3	48	27	75	42(87.5)	15(55.5)	57(76.0)
4	24	9	33	18(75.0)	9(100.0)	27(81.8)
>4	6	0	6	6(100.0)	0(0.0)	6(100.0)
Total	192	72	264	150(78.1)	51(70.8)	201(76.1)

Table 3. Urinary schistosomiasis by age and daily water contacts.

Age group in years	Number examined	Water contacts in a day					Total No.(%)Infect.
		1 No.(%)Infect.	2 No.(%)Infect.	3 No.(%)Infect.	4 No.(%)Infect	>4 No.(%)Infect.	
0-5	39	0(0.0)	3(4.0)	18(31.5)	3(11.1)	3(50.0)	27(13.4)
6-10	42	3(8.3)	12(16.0)	9(15.7)	9(33.3)	0(0.0)	33(16.4)
11-15	33	0(0.0)	3(4.0)	12(21.0)	9(33.3)	0(0.0)	34(16.9)
16-20	48	15(41.6)	15(20.0)	3(5.2)	0(0.0)	3(50.0)	36(17.9)
21-25	39	3(8.3)	12(16.0)	12(21.0)	6(22.2)	0(0.0)	33(16.4)
26-30	15	3(8.3)	9(12.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	12(5.9)
>30	48	12(33.3)	21(28.0)	3(5.2)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	36(17.9)
Total	264	36(17.9)	75(37.3)	57(28.3)	27(13.4)	6(2.9)	201(76.1)

Table 4. Age and sex reported haematuria.

Age group in years	Number examined			M	F	Total
	M	F	Total	No.(%)haem.	No.(%)haem.	No.(%)haem.
0-5	27	12	39	24(88.8)	9(75.0)	33(84.6)
6-10	21	21	42	18(85.7)	18(85.7)	36(85.7)
11-15	18	15	33	18(100.0)	15(100.0)	33(100.0)
16-20	45	3	48	33(73.3)	3(100.0)	36(75.0)
21-25	36	3	39	27(75.0)	3(100.0)	30(76.9)
26-30	12	3	15	9(75.0)	3(100.0)	12(80.0)
>30	33	15	48	21(63.6)	15(100.0)	36(75.0)
Total	192	72	264	150(78.1)	66(91.6)	216(81.8)

Table 5. Haematuria compared with parasitological detection of *S. haematobium*

	Haematuria (Yes)	Haematuria (No)	Total
Parasitological Positive	180	21	201
Parasitological Negative	36	27	63
Total	216	48	264

Sensitivity of haematuria = 83.33%, Specificity of haematuria = 42.85%, Positive predictive value of haematuria = 83.33%, Negative predictive value of haematuria = 56.25%, Percentage accuracy of haematuria = 78.41%.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Urinary schistosomiasis

Infection of urinary schistosomiasis was 76.1%, this showed that the area is endemic with the disease. The prevalence is high compared with a similar study conducted by [15] in the same geographical zone. This could be associated with differences in socio-cultural behaviour in the two study areas which may influence water contact activities essential for schistosomiasis transmission. In the same vein the findings concord with other parts of Nigeria; 74% in Gusau L.G.A of Zamfara State [8], 83.3% in Niger Delta [9], and contradicts the reports of Monday *et.al.*[10] and Akunfongwe *et.al.* [18] who reported prevalence rate of 15%, 2.4% in Bali Taraba State and Jos Plateau State respectively. The high prevalence obtained could be due to availability of factors in aiding the transmission of the disease. The location of Kiri dam in the area favours the breeding of snail intermediate host. The residents depends on the dam for their daily water activities, thereby exposing them to the urinary schistosomiasis. Another reason could be attributed to poor sanitary condition among the people for the continuous contamination of the area with indiscriminate defecation and urination. Also lack of health education and intervention programme contribute immensely to the prevalence of the disease in the area. From the result obtained there is an observable variation in the infection between males and females. This is similar with the reports of Odaibo *et.al.* [19], Sulyman *et.al.* [20], Ugbomoiko [21], Ekpo and Mafiana [11]. The higher infection in males than females is likely due to differences in water contact as indicated in the study. Men tend to swim, bath, farm and fish which exposes them to more infection. Besides, men stay longer in water for different activities than females. It was observed that infection was highest among participants in the age bracket of 21-25 years (84.6%) and lower among the age group of 0-5years (69.2%). The high prevalence observed in this age group could be due to prolong and high level of water contact behaviour. The residents engage in fishing almost twice daily and equally swim and bath in the water. The low infection among age group of 0-5 years (69.2%) may be because they consider themselves too young to engage in water activities like fishing, laundry and swimming which predisposes them to infection.

4.2 Relationship between infection rate and water contact each day

This study showed that infection of *S. haematobium* was more prevalent (100.0%) among individuals who had greater than four contacts with water every day, and least among those who had contacts with water twice each day (67.5%). This is not surprising as it was reported that people who had more contacts with water even though on different activities had higher chances of contacting urinary

schistosomiasis [22,23]. Infection based on daily water contact and age group showed that those who had contact with water twice every day were more infected than others. This may not be unconnected with the fact that visiting the dam twice every day by the respondents were more as shown in table 3 above probably because at no time people will not visit the river in the morning and evening for fishing, washing, fetching and bathing, thereby exposing the inhabitants to urinary schistosomiasis infection.

4.3 Haematuria in urinary schistosomiasis

During macroscopic examination of the urine samples it was revealed that 216 (81.8%) were bloody. This is on the higher side, an indication of endemicity of urinary schistosomiasis among the fishing community of Kiri dam. The reason for this high haematuria among the populace could be attributed to poor sanitary condition, the location of the area proximal to the dam, ignorance and daily activities in water. Again, there was ignorance about source of infection by the inhabitants. Many do not know exactly the cause of urinary schistosomiasis. In addition, strategies to control the prevalence of the disease has not been put in place. This is because the National Programme for its control has not been sustained due to political will by the policy makers to control the disease. Female had higher haematuria 66(91.6%) than males 150 (78.1%). The highest haematuria in females could be attributed to periodic menstrual cycle by females which mimic blood in urine that look like urinary schistosomiasis as there were higher infection rate in males than females. The age group between 11-15 years (100.0%) and 6-10 years (85.7%) recorded the highest number of those who had haematuria. These age groups were adolescents and school aged children. Hotez and Kamath [24] reported that the highest prevalence of schistosome occur in school aged children and adolescents. This is because they have regular contacts with water which exposes them to infection.

4.4 Haematuria compared to parasitological

Macroscopic detection of blood in urine without laboratory diagnosis can be used as a rapid diagnostic marker for the presence of *S. haematobium* infection. The sensitivity of 83.3%, specificity 42.8%, positive predictive value 83.3%, negative predictive value 56.2%, and percentage accuracy of 78.4% concord with the reports of Adeyemi *et.al.* [25], Guyatt *et.al.* [26], and Ekpo and Mafiana [11]. Passing out blood in urine may be sensitive and specific to be use where resources to diagnose *S. haematobium* is unavailable especially in remote areas where access to health care is difficult. Blood in urine in endemic areas of urinary schistosomiasis is an indication of infection. Its application could be use for the control of the disease [27,28]. Macroscopic detection of blood in urine may also be useful to exclude the low and high vulnerable areas of urinary schistosomiasis as

will as a diagnostic tool for urinary schistosomiasis.

5. CONCLUSION

This study has incriminated Kiri community in Shelleng local Government area of Adamawa State as endemic for urinary schistosomiasis. There is the need for immediate distribution of praziquantel to the infected residents. Proper health education on sanitary habits and mode of transmission of the disease is necessary as this will impact changes among the inhabitants of the area.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I wish to thank the officials of Kiri dam for the assistance rendered in the course of this research. I also thank the village head and residents of Kiri for their cooperation during the study. My thanks goes to Department of Medical Laboratory Science, Federal Medical Centre Yola, for the permission to analyse the samples in their Laboratory.

REFERENCES

1. Wiwanitkit, V.. Overview of Clinical Reports on Urinary Schistosomiasis in the Tropical Ashia. *Pakistan Journal of Medical Science*, 2005;21(4):499-501.
2. van der Werf MJ1, de Vlas SJ, Brooker S, Looman CW, Nagelkerke NJ, Habbema JD, Engels D. Quantification of clinical morbidity associated with schistosome infection in sub-Saharan Africa. *Acta Tropica*. 2003;86(2-3):125-39.
3. Engels, D., Chitsulo, L., Montresor, A. and Savioli, L. The global epidemiological situation of schistosomiasis and new approaches to control and research. *Acta Tropica*. 2002;82(2):139-146.
4. Steinmann, P., Keiser J., Bos, R., Tanner, M. and Utzinger, J. Schistosomiasis and water resources development: systematic review, meta-analysis, and estimates of people at risk. *Lancet Infectious Diseases*. 2006;6:411-425.
5. Utzinger, J., Raso, G., Brooker, S., de Savigny, D., Tanner, M., Ørnbjerg, N., Singer, B. H. and N'goran, E. K. Schistosomiasis and neglected tropical diseases: towards integrated and sustainable control and a word of caution. *Parasitology*. 2009;136:1859-1874.
6. Luke F. Pennington and Michael H. Hsieh. Immune Response to Parasitic Infections, Bentham e books, 2:93-124, ISBN 978-1-60805-148-9; 2014.
7. Donald G. McNeil, Jr. "Parasites: Giving a Deworming Drug to Girls Could Cut H.I.V. Transmission in Africa". *The New York Times*; 2009.
8. Bala, A. Y., Ladan, M.U. and Mainasara, M. Prevalence and intensity of urinary schistosomiasis in Abarme Village, Gusau, Nigeria: A Preliminary Investigation. *Science World Journal*. 2012;7(2):1-4.
9. Agi, P.I. and Okafor, J. The epidemiology of Schistosoma haematobium in Odua community in Niger Delta Area of Nigeria. *Journal of Applied Science and Environmental Management*, 2005;9(3):37-43.
10. Monday IE, Francis JI, Lamidi BT and Mohammed SU. Investigating Urinary Schistosomiasis in Bali Town, Bali Local Government Area, Taraba State, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Parasitology*. 2014; 35(1&2):149-155.
11. Ekpo, U.F. and Mafiana, C.F. Epidemiological studies of urinary schistosomiasis in Ogun State, Nigeria: identification of high-risk communities. *Nigerian Journal of Parasitology*, 2004;25:111-119.
12. Kramer, CV; Zhang, F; Sinclair, D; Olliaro, PL. "Drugs for treating urinary schistosomiasis.". *The Cochrane database of systematic reviews* 8: CD000053.doi:10.1002/14651858.CD000053.pu b3. PMID 25099517. accessed August, 6; 2014.
13. Akogun, O.B., and Akogun, M.K. Human behaviour water usage and schistosomiasis transmission in small settlement near Yola, Nigeria. *Annals of Tropical Medicine and Parasitology*. 1996;90(3):303-311.
14. Dunah, C. S. and Bristone, B. Prevalence of urinary schistosomiasis amongst primary school pupils in Mayo-Belwa L.G.A of Adamawa State. *Nigerian Journal of Parasitology*. 2000;21:15-20.
15. Pukuma, M. S. and Musa, S. P. Prevalence of urinary schistosomiasis among residents of Waduku in Lamurde Local Government Area of Adamawa State. *Nigerian Journal of Parasitology*. 2007;28(2):65-68.
16. NPC. The National Population of Nigeria, handle States individually. 2006.
17. Cheesbrough, M. District Laboratory Practice for Tropical countries University press Part 1, 2nd edition, Cambridge University Press, 2005, pp. 236-243.
18. Akunfongwe, P.E., Dondji, B., Okwuosa, W.B., Dakul, D.A. and Ntomifor, H.N. Observed disparity on schistosome infection rates in field Biomphalaria pfeifferi(Krass) between two areas of the Jos metropolis, Nigeria. *Parasite*. 1995;2:89:91.
19. Odaibo, A. B., Adewunmi, C., Olorunmola, F.O., Ademoyin, F.B., Olonfintoye, L.K., Akinwunmi, T.A., Adetula, M.O., Awe, C.O., and Akinyemi, F. Preliminary studies in the prevalence and distribution of urinary schistosomiasis in Ondo State Nigeria. *African Journal of Medical Science*. 2004;33(3):219-224.
20. Sulyman, M.A., Fagbenro-Beyioku, A.F., Mafe, M.A., Oyibo, W.A., Ajayi, M.B. and Akande, D.O. Prevalence of Urinary Schistosomiasis in school aged children in four States of Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Parasitology*. 2009;30(2):110-114.
21. Ugbomoiko, U. S. The prevalence, incidence and distribution of human urinary schistosomiasis in Edo State. *Nigerian Journal of Parasitology*. 2000;21:1-2.
22. Anya, A.O. and Okafor, F.C. Prevalence of Schistosoma haematobium infection in Anambra State, Nigeria. *Bulletin de l'Institut de fondamentale de Afrique Norie* A.1986;46:322-332.
23. WHO. The control of schistosomiasis. Second reports of the WHO expert committee. WHO Technical report series 830, WHO Geneva; 1993.
24. Hotez, P.J. and Kamath, A. Neglected Tropical Diseases in Sub-Saharan Africa: Review of their prevalence, distribution and disease burden. *Plos Neglected Tropical Disease*. 2009; 3(8): e412.doi 10.1371/journal.pntd0000412.
25. Adeyemi, E., Aisien, M.S.O. and Sam-Wobo, S.O. Evaluation of questionnaire, reagent strip and egg count as diagnostic techniques for confirming urinary schistosomiasis in school children, Edo State, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Parasitology*. 2014;35(1&2):47-52.
26. Guyatt, H., Brooker, S., Lwambo, N.J.S., Siza, J.E. and Donal, A.P. The performance of school-based questionnaires of self reported blood in

- urine in diagnosing *Schistosoma haematobium* infection: patterns by age and sex. *Tropical Medical International Health*. 1999;4(11):751-757.
27. Lengler, C., Utzinger, J. and Tanner, M. Screening for schistosomiasis with questionnaire. *Trends in Parasitology*.2002;18(9):375-377.
28. Lengler, C., Utzinger, J. and Tanner, M. Questionnaire for rapid screening of schistosomiasis in Sub-Sahara Africa. *Bulletin of World Health Organization*. 2002;80:235-377.